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THE THREE PHASES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SHAKER FURNITURE IN AMERICA, EUROPE, AND JAPAN

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ABSTRACT

Shaker furniture is a style of furniture that was made in America mainly in the nineteenth century.

However, it has since been introduced in various other countries, and the style has been applied in modern design theory. This article classifies the three phases in the development of Shaker furniture, and it clarifies the cultural elements that diversify the style as well as those that unify it in the twentieth century. These processes are developed through a search for the Shakers' philosophy and design, the contemporary discussions about them, and the cultural background of these discussions:

- (1) Furniture of functionalism
- (2) Furniture for home living
- (3) Furniture of Mingei

Each of them shows the diversity of the Shaker furniture. Conversely, the three phases described in the above Sections have factors that contrast with each other in the following manner:

- (1) The ideal aspect of functionalism discussed in Section 1 contrasts with the actual aspect of ergonomics discussed in Section 2.
- (2) The industrial aspect in Section 1 contrasts with the pre-industrial aspect in Section 3.
- (3) The user's viewpoint in Section 2 contrasts with the craftsman's viewpoint in Section 3.

The three phases are balanced and organized by each contrasts. This unity is appearing in the context of their cultural backgrounds; this is another aspect of diversity. Therefore, the three phases have two aspects of diversity and unity.

Keywords: The Shaker, Functionalism, Home living, Mingei.

INTRODUCTION

Edward Deming Andrews' *Shaker Furniture* (1937) and Timothy D. Rieman's *The Complete Book of Shaker Furniture* (1993) contained rich records of Shaker furniture, and described its history and craftsmanship. However, as the design historian John A. Walker pointed out, the study of the history of design developed with the acquisition of the knowledge of sociology, philosophy, engineering, and so on. Scholars and designers, who come from unique cultural backgrounds, have discussed Shaker furniture from various perspectives. Accordingly, this article emphasizes not only design but also philosophy of the Shakers, the discussions about them initiated by present-day contemporary scholars and designers, and the cultural backgrounds of these discussions. They can be classified into three phases and comprise three sections of this article. Thus, it can be clarified that the development of the Shaker furniture has two aspects of diversity and unity.

(1) FURNITURE OF FUNCTIONALISM

SIMPLICITY AS THE ETHIC

It was rare for Shakers to discuss beauty itself. The simplicity of the Shakers' designs was often described as an achievement of their ethics. The concept of simplicity is universal to the Shakers, and is linked with everything in their life, as indicated by maxims such as "we all ought to be simple and plain in our intercourse and conduct." The Shakers' ideas were systematized through twelve doctrines in "The Twelve Foundations of the Law of Christ" in A

Summary View of the Millennial Church as follows: “faith,” “hope,” “honesty,” “continenance,” “innocence,” “simplicity,” “meekness,” “humility,” “prudence,” “patience,” “thankfulness,” and “charity.” The doctrine of SIMPLICITY is placed at number six, and it comprises 25 lines (2nd edition). The clear universality of this doctrine is indicated by the following:

Its thoughts, words, and works are plain and simple.... It is without ostentation, parade, or any vain show, and naturally leads to plainness in all things.

Simplicity is described as “gospel simplicity” and “godly sincerity.” Such religious words and phrases also appear in the other eleven doctrines and in all the works describing the Shakers. The concept of simplicity was originally a part of the ethics of life.

SIMPLICITY AS AESTHETICS

Some exhibitions and writings about Shaker furniture analyzed their ethics of simplicity as design theory. The most typical aesthetic aspect of this was represented by functionalism.

In 1935, an exhibition of Shaker furniture was held in America. In the catalog for that show, Edward Deming Andrews described the Shaker’s philosophy as functionalism, showing the balance of beauty and usefulness through their maxims:

- The truly useful is always the truly beautiful.
- Beauty rests upon utility.
- That which has in itself the highest use possesses the greatest beauty.

As was mentioned earlier, the Shakers seldom referred to the concept of beauty. However, Andrews focused not on the concept of simplicity but on their functionalism. This perspective theoretically included Shaker furniture as part of the contemporary designs of the 1930s.

THE MODERN AMERICAN INTERIOR IN THE 1930S

Regarding contemporary interior design, the furniture manufacturer Herman Miller quoted Alfred Auerbach’s definition of modern design in his sales catalog: “good modern is quiet, rational, detached

from outmoded tradition, and essentially dedicated to logical forms evolved from a study of new living habits, the demands for comfort exacted from furnishings and the natural lines that certain materials properly employed, assume in design.” The design had to be intellectual, simple, and far from the decorations seen in the Federal style or the Victorian style. The comfort of life was achieved by the balance of usefulness in “furnishings” and beauty in the “natural lines.”

Herman Miller began to collaborate with Gilbert Rohde in 1932. He laid out every element in the modern rooms to ensure total harmony between the interior and the furniture design, since he believed that the background was as important as the product being displayed. Rohde was interested in the efficient use of wall space. For instance, the base of a bookcase unit was shallow, and designed to permit vertical stacking (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Pair of chests designed by Gilbert Rohde, Herman Miller Furniture Company, in 1937.

Consumers could choose from two finishes: a light, natural tone, or a light and dark combination. These bookcases also achieved the balance between usefulness (by allowing vertical stacking) and beauty (by allowing a choice in the pattern of finishes). Traditional style bedrooms required a separate wall for each item. Therefore, the most efficient use of room and wall space was ruled out. The modern arrangement grouped storage chests in pairs, or in groups of three (where feasible), overcoming this constraint, and making it possible to add a lounge chair and table, and twin beds, thereby adding to the comfort and functionality of the room.

Russel Wright was also active around this time. His “American Modern” range was mass-produced by Conant-Ball from 1935. Made of solid blanché maple, it comprised coordinated items for all parts of the house, unified by the overall use of plain, rectangular volumes, with rounded edges of wide

radius, and large, emphatic handles. He designed a series of oven-to-tableware in spun aluminum, and a range of ceramic dinnerware, all under the label “American Modern,” which were characterized by simple forms that emphasized the quality and finish of the materials used.

As was discussed earlier, the contemporary theory of interior beauty depended on coordinated items that were simply designed. Therefore, the interior was designed in a geometrical fashion, from the details of furniture to the overall space of the room. This was the main feature of functionalistic beauty. On the other hand, the contemporary theory of usefulness of the interior depended on getting rid of the vain space in a room. Furniture had to be neatly arranged for the full use of wall space.

SHAKER FURNITURE AS MODERN INTERIOR

The features described in these theories were seen in the Shaker furniture. For instance, with regard to beauty, the Shaker chair comprised two front posts, back posts, spindles, a slat back and a woven seat. Their four posts were thin and made of straight turned wood, and leaned slightly at the same angle. There were variations of this chair, such as the armchair and the rocking chair, but the basic design was uniform. Most cabinets and cupboards were plainly designed, and had no carvings (Figure 2-1); carvings were common in the traditional style. Further, the Shakers exploited the plainness of the cabinet, and built them into the wall. The built-in cabinet often created a square wooden pattern on the wall (Figure 2-2). They helped to get rid of vain wall space.

Figure 2-1. Drawers designed at Hancock.

Figure 2-2. Built-in cupboard designed at Hancock.

Their designs lent a geometrical order to the room. The Shakers’ interest in order was expressed in their maxims: “a place for everything and everything in its place,” “keep all things in order, as keeping the law of heaven; and the order of Zion, that heaven may protect you.” With regard to the usefulness of their furniture, the Shaker chair was light enough for a woman to move easily because of its design. They followed the custom of hanging the chairs on the wall, to clean the room efficiently. The straight back posts allowed them to be neatly hung on the plain wall (Figure 3). Plain cabinets or built-in cabinets were also ideal for efficient cleaning.

Figure 3. The Shakers had the custom of hanging chairs on the wall. The straight back posts and lightness of the chairs were suitable for this.

TWO ASPECTS OF AMERICAN DESIGN THEORY AND SHAKER FURNITURE

Functionalism has two aspects, and it would be unwise to consider Shaker furniture merely as an aspect. The American culture was too diverse to be represented by a singular ideology. A unique feature

of American Modernism was the number of generally contrasting ideas that were reflected in objects with widely varying appearances. Rationalism and the irrational, socialism and capitalism, objectivity and anonymity—they were all part of the idea of modernism. Rohde linked modernism to tradition, and argued, “modern furniture is our expression of the ancient and simple desire to make beautiful and useful things, suited to their purpose and to the materials and tools available.” To “make beautiful and useful” was not only a modern perspective but also an ancient and simple desire.

This idea is naturally seen in functionalism itself. The individual most often credited with constructing a theory of functionalism is the Chicago architect, Louis Sullivan. The roots of his ideas can be traced back to the early nineteenth century sculptor and natural philosopher, Horatio Greenough, who proposed that beauty arises as a direct response to the solution of a problem. He saw this relation between utility and aesthetics as a law of nature: “Beauty as the Promise of Function; Action as the Presence of Function; Character as the Record of Function.” Sullivan developed Greenough’s ideas. Sullivan wrote:

All things in nature have ... a form ... that tells us what they are, that distinguishes them from ourselves and from each other. Unfailingly in nature, these shapes express the inner life, the native quality of the animal, tree, bird, fish It seems ever as though the life and the form were absolutely one and inseparable ... form ever follows function, and this is the law.

Functionalism was theoretically linked to organic forms. It provided design with a symbol for an organic analogy. We can see the organic part and inorganic part in his architecture, such as The Sullivan Center (formerly known as the Carson, Pirie, Scott and Company Building). His work expressed the two aspects of functionalism, and blended the modern with the traditional. This represented the diversity of American Modernism.

Therefore, Shaker furniture was regarded as representing not only functionalism but also two ages. However, the commercial streamlined design was so strong that American design could not seriously

achieve the spirit of the functionalistic theory. Functionalism was a limited and short-term concept of product design. Thus, scholars retrospectively built up the ideal image of Shaker furniture. For instance, an exhibition in Europe was held in Germany in 1974. Writing in the catalog for this exhibition, Karl Mang classified the maxim “every force evolves a form” as an aspect of functionalism. This resembles the maxim “form follows function,” a phrase used by Louis Sullivan for this purpose. In 1990, the Britannica Encyclopedia described Shaker furniture thus: “their attitude toward design was based on religious beliefs, it anticipated in a remarkable way concepts of functionalism that became common about 100 years later.” Thomas Hauffe stated in *Design: A Concise History* (1998) that “A hundred years before the much-quoted formula of Luis Sullivan, ‘form follows function,’ pointed the way to the theory of functionalism, the Shaker religious community had laid down among the principle of its faith that ‘beauty arises from practicality.’”

(2) FURNITURE FOR HOME LIVING

SHAKER FURNITURE IN EUROPEAN MODERNISM

In 1944, the Danish designer Børge Mogensen designed the “Shaker Chair,” known as the J-39. This chair was designed for the Farmers’ Cooperative Association. The wide curve of the back and the simple construction of the chair itself made this piece particularly comfortable. The original design of the J-39 was a little chair that was often used in the dining room of dormitories at Shaker Village. Although certain aspects of both designs—such as the four posts and thin spindles—are similar, there are some differences between them. First, the J-39 was designed deeper and higher than the original Shaker chair, as shown below:

Size (mm)	W	D	H	Sh
Mogensen “Shaker Chair,” J-39	485	460	750	445
Original Shaker chair	478	373	651	414

Mogensen changed the original size of the chair to suit the body of a general user. Further, the back of

the J-39 was modified, and was wider than the original Shaker chair (Figure 4, left). This made the J-39 more comfortable (Figure 4, right).

Figure 4. (Left) The Shaker chair made at Mount Lebanon in the 1830s. (Right) J-39 designed by Danish designer Børge Mogensen in 1944.

ERGONOMIC PERSPECTIVE OF MOGENSEN AND THE KLINT SCHOOL

Mogensen studied under Kaare Klint at the Danish Royal Academy of Fine Arts. Mogensen's designs show the influence of Klint's ergonomic style.

In the design of the J-39, we can see some influences of the ladder back chair designed by Klint in 1936 (Figure 5).

Figure 5. The church chair designed by Kaare Klint in 1936.

The construction of the spindles and the weaving pattern of paper cord are the same as that of the J-39. However, the back of it was high and the two posts were bent. The back of J-39 was low and the posts were straight. This difference not only made it lighter and useful but also reduced the parts and made it affordable; the price of J-39 was 142 krone (oak) and 114 krone (elm) in the 1970's, and reasonable price for the general people whose national average of per income was about 70,000 krone.

Mogensen's drawings show the influence of ergonomics on his style. For instance, for designing furniture such as drawers or wardrobes, he measured common objects such as hats, gloves, shirts, and ties and included this aspect in the drawing. Further, the sizes of these items when they were folded or piled up were also checked and drawn. He focused on details about the actualities of the life of people to design furniture that was suitable for them.

Mogensen's method displays the influence of the Klint school of design. The curriculum of the Department of Furniture Design was developed from Klint's philosophy of design. His teaching combined both theoretical and practical concepts. The course started with students having to measure models of what were considered good chairs. This taught them to understand both the scale of the furniture and the scale of the human body, on which the design and construction of chairs are based. They then learned how to harmonize the scales of the things that are used in combination with furniture (lamp, vases, plates, etc.), and the scale of pieces of furniture in a group. They also measured the human body and adjusted the scale of the furniture according to its dimensions. These logical practices are known as ergonomics today.

As with American Modernism, their perspective also had influences from the past. Klint found particular beauty and rationality in the English furniture designs of the eighteenth century, and he made his students measure chairs designed by Chippendale and others. Similarly, Mogensen considered Shaker furniture to be furniture from the past. This perspective has two aspects: one is the perspective of ergonomics, and the other is the perspective of past masterpieces. This formed the background of the J-39. It was designed with a fusion of both perspectives.

SIMPLE ERGONOMICS FOR HOUSEWORK IN SHAKER FURNITURE AND INTERIORS

Svend Erik Moller regarded Mogensen's chair as "easy to handle and easy to keep clean." This shows that his design was actually successful. Housework was an important factor in designing furniture at that time. Naturally, similar perspectives were involved in the design of Shaker furniture. For instance, in *Seven American Utopias* (1976) and *The*

Grand Domestic Revolution (1982), the historian Dolores Hayden focused on how the Shaker's interior design helps housework. She described it was suitable for cleaning, as follows:

The construction details of the brick dwelling emphasize orthogonal ordering and easy maintenance. A wooden strip with pegs spaced twelve inches apart lines all walls about seven feet above the floor, providing a place to hang clothing, implements, or furniture. In the upstairs halls, these strips were hung with bonnets or hats.

Because pegs were installed seven feet from the floor, women could easily hang common objects, such as cleaning tools like a broom or a bucket, clothes, and so on. The Shakers had the custom of hanging chairs on the wall. Their chairs were designed to be light enough for women to be able to hang them. A chair was hung by holding it upside down, and hanging the spindle between the back posts on a peg (an exception was hanging the slat back on pegs, as seen at the exhibition in the museum).

Further, Hayden focused on several parts of the interior, which partly displayed the influence of ergonomics:

By providing consistent orthogonal organization, these strips consistently prevented more casual methods of using and storing objects. Large built-in storage cabinets provided more permanent storage in drawers of all sizes. Ever-present concern for economy of motion and materials is demonstrated by double-hung windows, fastened with wooden pegs, which could be unscrewed for quick washing and stairs built with small metal clips to hold strips of carpet on the treads, preserving the wood at points of wear.

She illustrated the usefulness of their interior design. The design to prevent "more casual methods of using" and their "concern for economy of motion" were based on a logical perspective regarding the user's behavior.

HOUSEWORK AND PHILOSOPHY

The Shakers considered cleaning to be special housework, and it had religious significance:

- Clean your room well; for good spirits will not live where there is dirt. There is no dirt in heaven.
- You ought to be neat and clean, for there are no slovens [sic] nor sluts in heaven.
- Provide place for your things.
- So that you may know where to find them at any time, by day or by night, and learn to be neat and clean, prudent and saving, and see that nothing is lost.

This shows that the Shakers regarded the interior as a sacred space, and emphasized cleaning as a sacred practice.

On the other hand, cleaning is not so sacred in modern life. Instead, the philosophy of present-day housework was discovered. In his work *The Poetics of Space* (1958), the French philosopher Gaston Bachelard asked "how [could] housework be made into a creative activity?" He focused on cleaning as the "integration of reverie into work," "our vastest dreams into the humblest of occupations." He quoted Henri Bosco's description: "The soft wax entered into the polished substance under the pressure of hands and the effective warmth of a woolen cloth. Slowly the tray took on a dull luster. It was as though the radiance induced by magnetic rubbing emanated from the hundred-year-old sapwood, from the very heart of the dead tree, and spread gradually, in the form of light, over the tray This was new creation of an object, a real act of faith, taking place before my enchanted eyes." Applying a shiny coat of wax on furniture is regarded as the "new creation of an object." Housework can bring out the beauty in furniture. Therefore the beauty of furniture was created not only by the design but also by housework.

The question of how modern Bachelard's perspective was can be resolved by considering Walter Benjamin's description of interiors. He realized that a microcosm was created in a room by the objects. They reflected the owner's ideals. The past interiors of aristocrats were not practical, but were full of ostentation and fantasy, like phantasmagoria. This includes the room called the

“Cabinet of Wonder” (also known as “Wunderkammer” in German), which displays objects of natural history, and so on. The focus was on the private ideal that each room had. Compared to this aspect of interiors, it is clear that the philosophy of housework is modern. Bachelard looked at the common life of people, and discovered a philosophical value in actual, common, and solid aspects of interiors.

(3) FURNITURE OF MINGEI

SANSHIRO IKEDA AND HIS PERSPECTIVE ON SHAKER FURNITURE

Sanshiro Ikeda (1909-1999) was one of the followers of the Mingei movement, a Japanese folk art movement. Mingei means “art of the people.” The movement started in 1926. Its purpose was to discover beauty in common handmade objects used in the past, and to apply it to create present-day handicrafts. Thus, the Mingei craftsmen aimed for a pre-industrial production. (The difference between the Mingei movement and the Arts and Crafts Movement of England will be discussed later.) The crafts ranged from pottery to woodwork, dyeing and weaving, woodcut, etc. Yanagi Soetsu (1889-1961), the founder of Mingei theory and a central figure of the movement, explored the folk crafts created by unknown craftsmen across Japan, and introduced them to the world. At that time, general art history had not yet acknowledged them.

Ikeda was different from the other followers of Mingei. Almost all of them were individual artists, known as “artist-craftsman,” but he was the manager of his factory. Ikeda employed unknown craftsmen, and trained them to create present-day Mingei.

In *Mingei no Kagu* (The Furniture of Mingei, 1973), Ikeda introduced Shaker furniture. He focused on the industrial aspect of the Shaker community:

the cultural background of furniture production was derived from far past faith. However, Shaker introduced mechanical skill into their life of community ... A part of industry was mechanized. Personal belief to sincere work and dedication to quiet and slow work was over in the end of eighteenth century. High technology of outside

world stimulated Shaker, and substituted for past inefficient ways. However, the attitude of industrial and agricultural enterprise was determined by their doctrine.

Ikeda focused on the introduction of machines to assist in handwork and the promotion of the official doctrine over the personal beliefs of people in the Shaker community.

THE INTRODUCTION OF MACHINES INTO HANDWORK

In accordance with Yanagi’s Mingei theory, Ikeda aimed to achieve the beauty of handwork but introduced the machines necessary to improve the factory’s productivity. If not, the Mingei products became so costly that the public could not buy and use them. This realistic determination resulted in achievements different from that of the Arts and Crafts Movement. Machines had to supplement handwork for efficiency. In this context, the definition of “pre-industrial” did not mean “anti-machine.” Ikeda aimed to create present-day pre-industrial products through a positive balance between man and machine.

How did he use machines? In Ikeda’s factory, machines were introduced only partly, so as not to affect the quality of handwork. The woodworking machine was used in the early processes of production. Automatic systems based on computer programming, such as the Numerical Control machining, were not introduced. However, power tools were used in the whole process. Because they helped the hand’s motion, power tools were regarded as a substitute for traditional tools such as saws, planes, and augers.

SHAKER FURNITURE AS PRESENT-DAY MINGEI

As mentioned earlier, Ikeda focused on the introduction of machines into the Shaker community; more accurately, he overlapped his handwork and that of the Shakers. There were no power tools in the nineteenth century, but the Shakers positively introduced woodworking machines. The Shakers used three types of machines: buzz or table saws, lathes, and mortisers. Because of their simple functions, they were used mainly in early processes such as sawing a log into lumber, or drilling holes in it. Handwork was done in skillful processes such as

smoothing wood, jointing the parts, and painting. The Shakers used a variety of tools:

- Cutting tools (saws, rips, crosscut, backsaw, bow saw)
- Planes (smoothing fore plane, jointing plane, plow plane, rabbet plane, panel plane, several molding planes)
- Drilling tools (brace and set of bits, gimlet)

The fact that they used a variety of tools shows that they were skilled at woodwork.

Further, the simple designs of Shaker furniture were suitable for keeping the balance between handwork and the use of machines. For instance, chairs were generally made of turned wood. Thus, the Shakers could easily make most of the parts by using only a lathe. For the rest of the processes, they smoothed them, jointed them, and finished them by hand. The furniture finally had the beauty of handmade items. Moreover, because of these processes, the Shakers could follow their doctrine that emphasized sincere work: "Put your hands to work, and your hearts to God."

Shaker furniture itself referred to folk crafts. The designs were derived from the Dutch style furniture of the colonial age. This style had the main features of the Shaker chair, such as the structure of woodturning, the finial on the back post, two or three slats at the back, and a seat woven out of tape made of wood. The Shakers modified these features simply and lightly for smooth production. Thus, the Shakers also studied the folk crafts of that time and designed their furniture to suit their handwork, the use of machines, and their doctrine.

For Ikeda, Shaker furniture was an inspiring product. It balanced the beauty of handwork and the efficiency of machines, and expressed their doctrine. The design was derived from past folk crafts made by unknown people. This was not a mere past folk craft but a notable example of present-day Mingei.

THE PERSPECTIVE OF ANTI MODERNISM AT THE INTRODUCTION OF SHAKER FURNITURE IN JAPAN

How was Shaker furniture introduced to Japan? The exhibition "Shaker Design" was held at the Saison Museum of Art in 1992. The catalog contained descriptions written by two curators. One was June

Sprigg, of the Hancock Shaker Village, and the other was Ryu Niimi, of the Saison Museum. Sprigg described her experience with the Shakers, providing details about their life. On the other hand, Niimi had no such experience. Instead, he discussed the Shaker designs from a various perspectives, such as folk art, Mingei, minimalism, and functionalism. This diversity seemed to derive from the manner in which Shaker furniture was introduced to Japan.

Shaker furniture was first introduced in Japan at the United States' pavilion at the World Exposition in 1970. The exhibition displayed a reproduction of the typical interior designs of the Shakers. Two slat back chairs were placed on the boarded floor, facing each other, and a butterfly table was placed between them. A slat back chair was hung on the wall. The built-in cases were reproduced on the wall. The slogan of the pavilion was the diversity of cultures, and it exhibited several American folk crafts called "while beauty and simplicity of hand produced, anonymous." Shaker furniture was thus introduced as a craft made by unknown craftsmen.

In 1973, Ikeda published above-mentioned *Mingei no Kagu*. That same year, and later in 1975, the furniture designer Teruaki Ohashi designed the "Koisu" (Little Chair, Figure 6). The four posts, two slat backs, thin spindles, the woven seat, and the overall proportion resemble the design of the Shaker chair for the dining room (Figure 4, left). The J-39 designed by Mogensen was similar to this chair (Figure 4, right). The chair made in 1975 was extremely light; he reduced the weight by getting rid of some of the spindles and by making the top of the back posts thinner. He also reproduced other Shaker slat back chairs.

Figure 6. Two "Koisu"(Little chair) were designed in 1973 (left) and 1975 (right). They show the influence of the Shaker chair for the dining room (Figure 4, left).

In 1974, the craftsman Hiroshi Fujikado established his farm in Hokkaido, and reproduced Shaker furniture and architecture.

In the same year, the architecture magazine SD ran a feature on Shaker furniture, which described the concise history of this style of furniture, relation between the designs and their doctrine, and decline of this style in the United States consequent to industrialization. This feature also included some descriptions written by Japanese designers and a poet. The furniture designer Riki Watanabe regarded it as the achievement of another crafts movement different from the Arts and Crafts Movement of England. The furniture designer Teruaki Ohashi showed the reproduction of a Shaker chair that he had made. He regarded it as an object outside modern design. The poet Shuntaro Tanikawa respectfully called his Shaker chair “a foreign object” in daily life, indicating that it “stood out” when arranged among objects of modern design. The efforts to popularize Shaker furniture in Japan continued in the 1970s after the World Exposition. Their theories included the perspective of anti modernism.

As above mentioned, a lot of craftsmen belonged to the Mingei movement, and the theories included the perspective of pre-industrial beauty. Niimi’s description was influenced by these ideals. Their ideologies were different, but they equally criticized past modernism.

In 1995, an exhibition of Shaker furniture and Mingei was held in America. Writing in the exhibition catalog, Martha W. Longenecker, a curator, mentioned that industrialization in America diminished the hand production of Shaker furniture. Similarly, while lecturing in America, Yanagi observed that many articles made by unknown craftsmen of pre-industrial times were of a beauty seldom equaled by the artists of modern societies.

CONCLUSION

The above sections can be summarized as follows:

- From Section 1 "Furniture of functionalism," it becomes clear that Shaker furniture was regarded as an ideal of modern industrial design, and not merely as a local craft of the Shaker community in America.

- From Section 2 "Furniture for home living," it becomes clear that Shaker furniture was a prototype of the modern lifestyle, which exhibited actual interests in the common life of people.
- From Section 3 "Furniture of Mingei," it becomes clear that Shaker furniture was regarded as having a pre-industrial and anti-modern craftsmanship.

Each of them shows the diversity of the Shaker furniture. Conversely, the three phases described in the above Sections have factors that contrast with each other in the following manner:

- The ideal aspect of functionalism discussed in Section 1 contrasts with the actual aspect of ergonomics discussed in Section 2.
- The industrial aspect in Section 1 contrasts with the pre-industrial aspect in Section 3.
- The user’s viewpoint in Section 2 contrasts with the craftsman’s viewpoint in Section 3.

The three phases are balanced and organized by each contrasts. This unity is appearing in the context of their cultural backgrounds; this is another aspect of diversity. Therefore, the three phases have two aspects of diversity and unity.

CHRONOLOGICAL TABLE

	Design	Book	Exhibition
1930's	[US]	The American furniture industry is a notable training ground for designers.	
1932	[US]	Herman Miller begins his collaboration with Gilbert Rohde, and brings out functionalistic designs.	
1935			[US] Whitney Museum of American Art holds an exhibition.
1937		[US] <i>Shaker Furniture</i> is published. The author, Edward D. Andrews, regards Shaker furniture as functionalist.	
1944	[EU]	Borge Mogensen designs the chair J-39, inspired by the Shaker chairs for the dining room.	
1958	[EU]	<i>The Poetics of Space</i> is published. The author, Gaston Bachelard discovers the philosophy of present-day housework.	
1961			[US] The community (Hancock) opens to the public.
1962			[US] The permanent exhibition at Philadelphia Museum of Art begins.
1968			[US] The community (Pleasant Hill) opens to the public.
1970			[JPN] The Shaker's interior is reproduced at the United States' pavilion at the World Exposition in Osaka.
1973		[JPN] <i>Mingei no Kagu (The Furniture of Mingei)</i> is published. The author, Sanshiro Ikeda, introduces Shaker furniture as an example of Mingei.	
	[JPN]	Teruaki Ohashi reproduces the Shaker chair. He designs new chairs inspired by it in 1975.	
1974			[EU] An exhibition is held in Munich, Germany.
		[JPN] The architecture magazine <i>SD</i> runs a feature on Shaker furniture.	
	[JPN]	Hiroshi Fujikado, a craftsman, establishes his farm in Hokkaido, and starts reproducing Shaker furniture and architecture.	
1976		[US] <i>Seven American Utopias</i> is published. The author, Dolores Hayden, describes the relation between the interior design and the lifestyle of the Shakers.	
1980's	[EU]	Furniture manufacturer De Padova starts reproducing Shaker furniture.	
1981			[US] The Metropolitan Museum of Art, American Section, opens to the public.
1982		[US] <i>The Grand Domestic Revolution</i> is published. The author, Dolores Hayden, describes the Shakers' socialized housework.	
1992			[JPN] Saison Museum of Art (Tokyo) holds an exhibition.
		[JPN] <i>Shaker enoTabi (The Journey for Shaker)</i> , the first book by a Japanese author (Hiroshi Fujikado) on Shaker furniture is published.	
1993	[US]	<i>The Complete Book of Shaker furniture</i> is published. The author, Timothy D. Rieman, improves Andrews's study.	
1995			[US] The Mingei International Museum of World Folk Art holds an exhibition. It showcases Shaker commodities and Mingei products.
1996		[JPN] <i>The Book of Shaker Furniture</i> (author: John Kassay) is translated to Japanese (translator: Hiroshi Fujikado).	
1998	[EU]	<i>Design: A Concise History</i> is published. The author, Thomas Hauffe, discusses the functionalism in Shaker thought.	

[US]:United States of America, [EU]:Europe, [JPN]:Japan.

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